

Is Entropic Disorder Due to an Observer's Information Scheme or a State Property?

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Entropy is often said to be linked to “disorder”, i.e. higher entropy means more disorder. We try to investigate what disorder means. We consider a simple example of 26 encyclopedia books and argue that order is linked to an observer's information scheme or map and is not an intrinsic state of the system. In other words, it is relative to the observer's information in this particular example. We further consider the information required for a map or information scheme as data not necessarily linked to entropy which requires probabilities in Shannon's picture (and also Boltzmann's). For example, an ordering of the books may represent disorder and entropy to a person with one information map or scheme, but complete order to another observer with a different map or information scheme. In one case, there are probabilities and entropy and in the other case, no probabilities and zero entropy.

We also consider the case of photons passing through a two-slit apparatus. If one does not follow each photon in time, or is interested in the relative numbers of photons at different screen positions, then there is entropy. If one only measures that N photons hit the screen, regardless of where and when, then there is no probability and entropy. If one has a set of N photons sent in one at a time, these are correlated (described by one information scheme or map which states that all photons have p momentum pointing in the y direction). After scattering, the information scheme or map for identical photons is different, (it is based on the interference pattern), but this simply means that one changes maps or information schemes. There is no probability unless one can resolve time such that one tries to predict what each photon does or deals with relative numbers of photons at different screen positions. Thus, entropy seems to be linked with resolution in a measurement.

Coin or Die Toss

One may use Shannon's entropy formula to calculate entropy for a coin toss or die roll. Entropy exists because one does not know the outcome and so different outcomes, each with a probability, exist. It does not seem, however, that there is any disorder created as a coin lies on one side or the other and the same for a die. It is just that the observer's information scheme has been broken. If the coin is initially heads, then after the toss it might be heads or tails. This entropy is about the observer's information, not about any state disorder in the physical system, we argue.

Set of Encyclopedias

Consider a set of 26 encyclopedia books. In order to have order, one might suggest that one knows the (x,y) coordinate of the first A book and then has the rest of the books arranged to the right in alphabetical order. In other words, this so-called order is an information scheme or map which is convenient for a particular observer. There does not seem to be any reason why 26 physical books need to be adjacent to one another or to be arranged alphabetically. In fact, one may place these 26 books at any 26 (x,y) co-ordinate pairs as long as one writes a map or

information scheme on a piece of paper, arranged alphabetically with each letter given an (x,y). This is a different map or information scheme and is linked with one set of arrangements of the books. This is an ordered situation to the second person, but disorder to the first person. Thus, we argue that disorder is not necessarily a state property.

We do, however, point out that different maps or information schemes may involve different amounts of information. In the first scheme, one requires (x1,y1) for the first book, knowledge of the order of the alphabet and that the subsequent book sit to the right.

In the second scheme, one requires 26 (x,y) pieces of information and also information about the order of the alphabet and a linking of each letter with each (x,y). This represents much more information, but both schemes represent order to the person holding the particular map.

A person with the map of the 26 (x,y) pieces would suggest that there is complete order. A person with the first information scheme would suggest that there is entropy even if given the 26 (x,y) points because one may arrange the 26 books at these points in different ways. If the person is not given the (x,y) points, then each of the 26 books could be at any (x,y) point (no overlap) which would mean even more entropy (or disorder according to the first person). In other words, entropy (or disorder) seems to be relative to the observer in this example.

We do suggest that even though entropy is relative to the observer in these examples, that one may define a measure:

Information in a map ((1))

((1)) holds even if there is no entropy, i.e. no probability. Some maps or schemes require much more order to define order.

Two-Slit Interference

Consider a situation in which N photons (N being very large) are sent one after the other towards a 2-slit apparatus. Each of the photons has p in the y direction, i.e. their information scheme is correlated. As each photon goes through the 2-slit apparatus, there is a probability that it will change its p direction (not magnitude) and arrive at some position on a horizontal (x direction) screen some distance away.

We first note that the idea of probability only applies to each photon considered separately. If one considers all N photons and knows the map or information scheme of the interference pattern, then one knows exactly how many photons hit each region of the screen. Thus, by not following each photon individually and only looking at a collective result, the map or information scheme of this collective result is enough to know with certainty how many photons arrive at each point. It is only if one is worried about the details of the order in which the photons reach the different points does the idea of probability arise. This is the same situation for an N set of trial runs of tossing a coin or die. One knows that .5N of the time the coin will be heads up and .5N of the cases, tails and a similar idea for the die. The notion of entropy appears by writing the probability for a trial run and then taking its ln i.e.

$\ln(\text{probability of an N trial run}) = \ln\{ .5^{\text{power}(N,5)} * .5^{\text{power}(N,5)} \}$

$$= \ln \{ \exp(.5N \ln(.5) + .5N \ln(.5)) \} \quad ((2))$$

The first factor represents heads and the second, tails. All probability products for any N trial run yield the same $\ln(\text{probability})$ which is linked to entropy, i.e.

$$.5 \ln(.5) + .5 \ln(.5) \text{ multiplied by } -k \text{ is entropy} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, one knows with certainty that .5N are heads and .5N are tails and if this is all one is concerned about, then this is an information scheme and one does not really have any probability.

The notion of entropy arises if one cares about the probability product (or \ln of this value) for the N runs. This turns out to be N times the average $\ln(\text{probability of single toss})$ value. This latter value is called information in information theory and so entropy is a measure related to the average value of the \ln of the various probabilities involved in the problem, assuming that one is interested in these probabilities.

For example, if one does not care whether the outcome of coin toss is a head or tail, then N tosses have no probability associated with them whatsoever. Similarly for the N photons which pass through a 2-slit apparatus, one knows that all N will reach a screen. If one does not care at which point they strike, then there is no probability and no information scheme. If one is not interested in the order in which the photons hit various regions, then there is again no sense of probability, but one does need the overall interference pattern (which is a probability distribution) to know how many photons will hit each region. The probability pattern, however, is not an entropy expression. Entropy is given by Shannon's formula:

$$-k \sum_i f(i) \ln(f(i)) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, entropy and probability seem to be linked with resolution (e.g. space) and biases (e.g. different numbers of photons) linked with the resolution. There is still probability even with no bias, but with resolution. For example, a uniform probability distribution exists in such a case, but one must have a resolved variable on the x-axis and probability on the y. In other words, one seems to distribute some quantity over a resolved range of another variable.

Is There Disorder in the 2-Slit Situation?

One may ask whether or not there is disorder in the 2-slit experiment. If one is only interested in the fact that one has N photons with energy $E=pc$ at the beginning and N photons with energy $E=pc$ at the end, regardless of where they hit the screen, then there is no loss of information or any sense of disorder.

If one considers that at the beginning the N photons are correlated, i.e. all have p magnitude in the y direction, but after going through the 2-slit apparatus, extra information is required, i.e. certain numbers are associated with each angle with the y-axis, then the information scheme has changed, but again there is no sense of probability because one does not think in terms of a single photon. In other words, an information scheme with two pieces of information for N photons, namely p magnitude and the y direction, is replaced with a set: $\{n_i, \theta_i\}$.

It is only if one is concerned about each photon and where it lands on a screen that one has probability or if one is concerned with the relative number of photons reaching different points on the screen that one has the notion of probability. In other words, one has to resolve time or space in order to sense probabilities in this case. One resolves time if one follows each photon, and space if one considers the number of photons that hit each spatial region of the screen. Without probability, one has no entropy calculation.

Thus, we argue that probability and hence entropy and the notion of disorder depend on the observer and the type of measurement he or she is interested in. For certain measurements which do not resolve time or space, there is no probability or entropy, i.e. the case that one only needs to know that N photons hit the screen in a certain amount of time regardless of where they land. Furthermore, from the point of view of following a single photon, even though one does not know which angle it will receive after passing through the 2-slit apparatus, the photon initially moves in a straight line with momentum p and is later moving in a straight line with momentum p . In other words, from the physical point of view of a single photon, there is no extra disorder as we have pointed out in a previous note. The probability of θ means that the observer is not sure in which direction the photon will move.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that entropy depends on the existence of probabilities and these in turn depend on the type of measurements that an observer is able to make. For example, we note that for N photons passing through a 2-slit apparatus, if the observer only cares that N photons reach a screen without worrying about how many arrive in one region or another, then there is no sense of probability or entropy. It is only if one resolves the number of photons which arrive at different spatial points or follow each photon in time that one notices probability and hence entropy (created from probability). Thus, we suggest that entropy may be linked to the observer's measurements (i.e. what is resolved).

We also consider the notion of entropy being linked with disorder. We suggest that physically there may be no disorder, but that an observer's map or information scheme no longer matches the physical situation which leads to the idea of probabilities and hence entropy appearing. Furthermore, we argue that there exist cases for which one map or information scheme may no longer match the arrangement of objects, but another does. In such a case, there may be probabilities and entropy for the first observer, but not for the second (as in the case of encyclopedia books discussed above).